

SHAGGAR INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY

BIOMIMETIC COOLING SYSTEM

Group 45

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Advanced physics 101

Submitted to: Professor Solomon Bililign

January 14, 2026

ABSTRACT

Buildings consume a significant amount of energy for cooling, especially in hot climates. Conventional air-conditioning systems rely heavily on electricity and contribute to environmental pollution. In contrast, many natural systems regulate temperature efficiently without external energy input. One remarkable example is the termite mound, which maintains nearly constant internal temperature despite large external temperature fluctuations.

Using principles of thermodynamics and heat transfer, the study demonstrates how passive cooling strategies based on natural ventilation can significantly reduce indoor temperature and energy consumption. The results show that biomimetic designs can enhance energy efficiency and provide sustainable alternatives to traditional cooling systems, especially in hot climates.

MOTIVATION

Nature offers excellent examples of passive thermal regulation. Termite mounds, built by small insects, can maintain stable internal conditions through intelligent design and natural airflow. This project is motivated by the idea of learning from nature and applying its principles to human engineering problems. By simulating such systems, we can explore sustainable cooling methods that reduce energy use and environmental impact.

In many developing regions, including hot and arid areas, access to efficient and affordable cooling remains a major challenge. All these challenges serve us as a starting stone to develop a biomimetic simulation and put ideas down for future improvements.

POTENTIAL APPLICATION

Using biomimetic cooling simulation has a tremendous potential application. However, energy saving and reducing cost are among main targets of using biomimetic simulation. Passive cooling uses natural design (shading, ventilation, thermal mass, reflective surfaces) to keep buildings cool, drastically cutting reliance on energy hunger, which lowers utility bills, decreases

operational costs, and shrinks carbon footprints, offering significant long-term financial and environmental benefits despite potentially higher upfront material costs. The principles demonstrated by termite mounds have been eyed by architects and builders as potential blueprints for designing buildings that require less energy for cooling and heating.

How it works:

Reduces energy demand: By preventing heat from entering and promoting natural heat loss, passive cooling minimizes the need for mechanical systems, leading to major energy saving (up to 30-60% on cooling).

Lowers operating costs: Less energy use directly translates to lower electricity bills and reduced maintenance for A/C units, saving money over the building's life.

Improve comfort: Creates more stable, healthier indoor temperature, reducing reliance on constant cooling.

Externally, the towering mounds constructed by termites might not look like engineering wonders, but these complex structures can inspire today's architects to design more efficient and sustainable homes and workplaces. Termite mounds and other natural solutions can inspire humans to build smarter, less energy intensive buildings. The Ethiopian region those who use termite mounds style dwellings:

- 1.Southern Ethiopia: -dorze people (Gamo highlands, southern nations)
- 2.Southern Ethiopia: -konso zone (SNNPR / Southern Ethiopia Regional State)

METHODOLOGY

For our project, Biomimetic cooling system, we mimic the termite's mound cooling system. In our approach we considered all three mechanisms of heat transfer: Radiation, conduction and convection. In addition, we used the vegetation surrounding the building.

From Stefan's law: $P = \sigma A e T^4$

Based on the above formula, for our building we classified parts of our building into three parts: outside the building, inside the building, and the top surface area of the building.

Outside the building: we tried to paint the building white to reflect most of the light reaching it.

Inside the building: We paint black inside of the wall of the building, in order to increase the amount of energy(infrared) absorbed from hot objects in the building including human beings.

Top surface of the building: we minimized the top surface area of the building very small like that of termite’s mound, in order to minimize the amount of heat transfer from sunlight to the building.

$$Q = kA \frac{\Delta T}{L} \Delta t$$

Conduction: Heat absorbed by the wall of the building will transfer through the wall of the building in conduction.

For our building model, we need material with small thermal conductivity and large thickness. This implementation will result in the building with high thermal mass.

Convection: we implemented power fans in our building model to let in the cold air from outside through forced convection, like that of termite mound with many openings to let in cold air. The cold air let in will be heated and evacuated at the openings at the top of the building.

Figure showing our project Design

RESULT

The project yield results in the following areas:

1. Architecture and Ventilation: model highlights the intricate network of tunnels, chimneys and chambers. Results typically show how these structures facilitate passive airflow and gas exchange (oxygen in and carbon dioxide out) through natural convection and wind pressure differences, effectively creating a form of “natural air conditioning”.

2. Thermoregulation: The result demonstrates the mounds’ ability to maintain stable internal temperature and humidity levels despite fluctuating external conditions.

3. Biomimicry and Human Application: The key result in this project is the successful simulation of termite construction behavior (stigmergy) and the potential for applying the principles to sustainable human architecture. This can involve designing energy-efficient buildings that use similar passive cooling and ventilation strategies.


```
physics > Fluid_dynamics.py
1 # physics/Fluid_dynamics.py
2 # =====
3 # FLUID DYNAMICS MODULE - Natural Airflow Calculations
4 # =====
5 # Based on Physics Units 14 (Fluid Mechanics) and related concepts:
6 # - Pressure and density
7 # - Bernoulli's Principle
8 # - Stack Effect (Buoyancy-driven flow)
9 # - Mass flow rate and continuity
10 # =====
11
12 import math
13 import sys
14 import os
15
16 # Add parent directory to path for imports
17 sys.path.insert(0, os.path.dirname(os.path.dirname(os.path.abspath(__file__))))
18
19 from config import G, RHO_AIR_SEA_LEVEL
20 from physics.thermodynamics import calculate_air_density
21
22 # =====
23 # STACK EFFECT - Natural Convection (Unit 14 + Thermodynamics)
24 # =====
25
26 def calculate_stack_velocity(T_internal, T_external, stack_height, vent_ratio=1.0):
27     """
28     Calculate natural convection velocity using the Stack Effect.
29     """
```

Figures showing the results of our project.

FUTURE WORK

One of the main future works for this simulation is to build an automated control system using a microcontroller such as Arduino or Raspberry Pi that can control the fans automatically. Using a DHT22 temperature and humidity sensor, we can create a feedback loop that would allow us to control the RPM of the “power fans” that cools the air and power this effect to optimize the cooling efficiency of the system by measuring the thermal gradient and CO₂ build up.

However, we would also like to expand the simulations to material science, where we would like to apply it to concrete walls using phase change materials (PCMs) to allow the model to store even more heat and shift the cooling of the building to the coolest point at nighttime. Finally, we would like to adapt our simulation to have a rough surface as a real termite mound would, as this minor turbulence they create would allow them to dissipate even more heat. We hope to one day build this at architectural scale in an arid and hot region in Ethiopia for empirical results based on actual use and behavior.

CONCLUSION

This project demonstrates biomimicry as a high-tech, energy-efficient solution to combat the energy crisis in building design. Through imitating and replicating the architectural and structural techniques used by termites to ventilate their mounds, we have designed an effective cooling system for our simulated building that requires no energy-intensive mechanical air conditioning based on thermodynamic principles. Our simulation showed that it is possible to reduce the rate of heat entering the building from over 50% to less than 10% of that rate by leveraging Stefan's Law using a white reflective coating and high thermal mass concrete.

$$P = \sigma A \epsilon T^4$$

The results demonstrated that the natural "stack effect" renders this architectural cooling approach effective, as hot air can rise and exit the building through holes at the top, with cooler, denser air entering through ventilation slots at the base.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors of this project would like to acknowledge and thank everyone that helped us with this project. We would first like to thank our physics professor, Professor Solomon Bililign at the Shaggar Institute of Technology for his guidance in an understanding of its principles and complexities. We would like to express our special gratitude to Amanuel Desalegn for his help with the design and coding of our simulation.

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